

SETAC EUROPE 35TH ANNUAL MEETING

11-15 MAY 2025 | VIENNA, AUSTRIA | [SETAC.ORG/VIENNA](https://setac.org/vienna)

INNOVATION FOR TOMORROW: PROGRESS IN SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE CONCEPTS

ABSTRACT BOOK

contaminated medium. Fertility was determined by crossing exposed virgin flies with control virgin flies and scoring progeny over 15-days. For adults, the LC50 values for GBH Gallup were determined as 6.53mg/mL for female and 6.97mg/mL for male flies. Similarly, the LC50 for GBH Roundup was determined as 5.9mg/mL for female and 5.65mg/mL for male flies. Exposure of laid eggs to sublethal doses (0.01-5mg/mL) of Gallup and Roundup led to dose dependent declines in egg and larval survival. With 5mg/mL concentrations leading to 100% and 61% lethality respectively and 1mg/mL concentrations leading to 75% and 35% lethality respectively. Furthermore, exposure to sublethal doses of GBHs during development produced adults with impaired fertility. Females exposed to 1mg/mL Gallup or Roundup during development have 34 and 40% declines in their fertility rates. Similarly exposed males have 75 and 57% reductions in their fertility rates. Sublethal doses of GBHs have significant effects on *Drosophila* development and fertility. The formulation Gallup has a higher toxicity than that of Roundup and there are sex-specific differences in response rates to GBH exposure. Ongoing experiments aim to identify the molecular mechanisms of this reproductive toxicity. This study improves our understanding of glyphosate-induced reproductive effects and the potential effects of sublethal doses of these pesticides on insects. This Project is Currently Funded by the TUS Presidential Doctoral Scholarship.

1.01.P-Tu008 Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Evaluation of Rock Powders Used in Agriculture in Brazil: Preliminary Results with *Enchytraeus crypticus* and *Folsomia candida*

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In alignment with the principles of the Circular Economy, there is a growing expectation that waste generated in the mineral sector will not only be properly managed but also be repurposed into new production cycles. However, many materials from this sector contain naturally occurring chemicals from rocks that may pose potential toxicity. Rock powders, derived from rock extraction activities, are approved for agriculture application in Brazil as fertilizers or secondary materials. Despite this, ecotoxicological tests are not mandated under Brazilian legislation, and studies on their ecotoxicity remain limited. This lack of information is particularly concerning due to the potential long-term effects and impacts throughout the food chain. This study aims to conduct preliminary ecotoxicological tests of rock powders deemed for agriculture use, employing terrestrial organisms *Enchytraeus crypticus* and *Folsomia candida*, in accordance with ABNT standards NBR ISO 16387:2012 Soil quality Effects of pollutants on Enchytraeidae (*Enchytraeus* sp.) Determination of effects on reproduction and survival, and ABNT NBR ISO 11267:2019 Soil quality Inhibition of reproduction of Collembola (*Folsomia candida*) by soil pollutants. The materials were ground and sieved to ensure that at least 50% of particles were less than 0.3 mm in size. The major oxide composition included SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and Fe₂O₃. Tests were conducted by mixing the rock powder samples with Tropical Artificial Soil (TAS) at the concentrations of 0%, 0.1%, 1.0%, 10%, and 100%. Preliminary testing of three samples (SC, MG, and GE) sourced from different mining operations in Brazil (Santa Catarina, Minas Gerais and Rio de Janeiro) revealed no chronic toxicity for *E. crypticus* in any samples. However, at concentration of 100%, samples MG and GE exhibited significant chronic toxicity for *F. candida* ($p < 0.05$), with a reduction in reproduction (ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test). Complementary chemical analyses and other ecotoxicological tests need to be performed. These screening and preliminary findings highlight the importance of appropriate application rates for rock powders and integrating biological indicators into the registration process for all agricultural fertilizers and inputs in Brazil. Such measures are vital to prevent potential adverse effects on biotic communities in agricultural ecosystems while ensuring that sustainability and safety principles are upheld in the reuse of these materials. Center for Mineral Technology (CETEM/MCTI); National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq) for PCI-DA Scholarship from the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation (MCTI) of Brazil.

1.01.P-Tu009 Linking Molecular and Phenotypic Endpoints in Zebrafish Larvae Exposed to Ciprofloxacin and Cadmium

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The EPIBOOST project aims at validating the epigenetic modifications caused by chemicals as biomarkers of relevance which can support more accurate environmental risk analysis. For this, a multiparametric approach is pursued by looking at the effects of chemicals from the individual and biochemical levels to the genetic and epigenetic levels, establishing a link between phenotypic and molecular endpoints. In this work, taking ciprofloxacin (CIP) and cadmium (Cd) as a case study, 96 hours zebrafish larvae were exposed to sublethal concentrations of the CIP (ranging from 10 to 50 mg/L) and Cd

(0.24 to 24 µg/L) for 24 hours. Endpoints analysed included mortality, development, swimming behaviour (swimming distance and path angles), biotransformation enzymes (glutathione-s-transferase (GST)), antioxidant enzymes (catalase (CAT), and glutathione reductase (GR)), neurotoxicity markers (acetylcholinesterase (ChE)), transcriptomics and DNA methylation. For Both chemicals, at concentrations tested no effects on survival or development (delays or anomalies) were observed. CIP induced an activation of the antioxidant system which seemed to have occurred as suggested by the increase in the CAT activity. In contrast to Cd which decreased the CAT activity. In the same direction, an increase in ChE activity was also observed in eleutheroembryos exposed to CIP, while Cd induced a reduction in the ChE activity suggesting neurotoxicity elicited by the tested Cd concentration. The study of swimming behaviour indicated an alteration of the swimming pattern, where zigzag movements and high-speed movements increased suggesting an anxiety-like behaviour of larvae exposed to the antibiotic. Molecular analyses are underway to further elucidate transcriptomic changes and DNA methylation profiles associated with these phenotypic and biochemical alterations.

1.01.P-Tu010 Effects of Bisphenol S (BPS) in the Threespine Stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*): Exploring the Links Between Biomarker and Life History Traits Responses

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Chemical pollutants in aquatic environments disrupt biomarkers, affecting growth, reproduction, and survival. Bisphenol S (BPS), a substitute for bisphenol A (BPA), has been linked to reproductive impairments, metabolic disruptions, oxidative stress, and immune dysfunction in fish. This study investigates BPS effects on biomarkers and life-history traits in three-spined stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*) to establish mechanistic links across biological scales. Three experiments were conducted: (1) a 6-month mesocosm study exposing fish to BPS (0, 1, 10, 54 µg/L) in artificial streams, assessing biomarkers like immune parameters, respiratory burst, and organ mass; (2) a 21-day caging study in mesocosms examining reproductive and oxidative stress biomarkers; and (3) a 40-day laboratory study (BPS: 0, 1, 10, 100 µg/L) assessing biomarkers and linking them to life-history traits such as stickleback nest construction in males and oocyte maturation in females. The mesocosm experiment revealed altered respiratory burst, reduced immune cell counts, and impaired phagocytic function in both sexes, suggesting immunosuppression, with females also exhibiting cells necrosis. In the 21-day study, both sexes showed signs of altered antioxidants, with females showing effects at low doses (1 µg/L). Laboratory experiments revealed significant effects on reproduction, metabolism, and links between biomarkers and life history traits. Dose-dependent effects included reduced gonado-somatic index (GSI) and sperm count in males, alongside increased nephrotic-somatic index (NSI) and variability in nest characteristics (weight, surface area). In females, hepatosomatic index (HSI) increased significantly, while mature oocyte count and GSI increased at higher doses. The study revealed effects of BPS on reproduction, metabolism, oxidative stress, respiratory burst and phagocytic activity, and allow to establish link biomarkers to life-history traits. This approach aims to model population-level impacts and extrapolate findings to other pollutants, enhancing environmental risk assessment. This project has also received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101057014 (The European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals; PARC).

1.01.P-Tu011 Embryonic Exposure to the Endocrine Disrupting Chemical, TBCO, Causes an Intrageneration Decrease in Reproductive Performance of Female Japanese medaka (*Oryzias latipes*) by Impairing Oocyte Maturation

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Vitellogenesis and oocyte maturation are the final two steps of oogenesis in fish. Most studies of reproductive toxicity focus on the disruption of vitellogenesis leading to decreased fecundity, with very little focus on oocyte maturation, the final stage of oogenesis that gives rise to a fertilizable oocyte. Previous studies from our group demonstrated that reduced fecundity of Japanese medaka exposed as embryos to maternally transferred TBCO, a brominated flame retardant, was caused by impairment of maturation-inducing hormone (MIH)-induced oocyte maturation. However, the molecular mechanism(s) of this effect are unknown. The objective of this research is to investigate the molecular basis of decreased oocyte maturation leading to reduced fecundity in Japanese medaka exposed as embryos to maternally deposited TBCO. F0 generation fish were fed a 100 or 1000 µgTBCO/g diet for 21 days. F1 generation embryos collected during the final week of the exposure were reared to sexual maturity in clean water without any additional exposure to TBCO. At sexual maturity, reproductive performance was assessed in a standard 21-day reproduction assay, after which an ex-vivo oocyte maturation assay was performed. To elucidate mechanisms of decreased oocyte maturation, high-throughput RNA sequencing and enzyme-

Larvae Exposed to Ciprofloxacin and Cadmium

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BACKGROUND

The EPIBOOST project aims at validating the epigenetic modifications caused by chemicals as biomarkers of relevance which can support more accurate environmental risk analysis. To do so, a multiparametric approach is pursued by looking at the effects of chemicals from the individual and biochemical to the transcriptomic and epigenetic level, with the aim to establish a link between phenotypic and molecular endpoints.

RESEARCH Aims

Using zebrafish eleutheroembryos we aim to evaluate developmental, behavioural, biochemical, transcriptomic and DNA methylation effects to later relate to molecular effects resulting from **cadmium** (Cd) and **ciprofloxacin** (CIP) exposures.

METHODS

Exposure: 96 hours post fertilization zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) eleutheroembryos exposed for 24 h to Cd (ranging from 0.24 to 24 µg/L) and CIP (10 to 50 mg/L). Exposures were performed in 6-well plates (10 individuals/well). At the end of the exposure 16 biological replicates (10 embryos/sample) per experimental group were collected and flash frozen.

Biochemical and molecular endpoints:

- 8 biological replicates/group were used for the determination of biotransformation enzymes activity by colorimetric assessment including: glutathione-s-transferase (GST), antioxidant enzymes catalase (CAT), glutathione reductase (GR) and superoxide dismutase (SOD), peroxidative damage by lipid peroxidase activity (LPO) and neurotoxicity markers as acetylcholinesterase (AChE).
- RNA/DNA extraction was performed from 8 biological replicates/group. Transcriptomics were assessed by a real-time microfluidic platform (total of 96 genes) and global DNA methylation by MethylFlash™ Global DNA Methylation (5-mC).

Behavioural endpoints: 24 organisms (individually exposed) per treatment.

Basal locomotor activity and swimming patterns assessed using the **Zebbox** video tracking system.

Swimming patterns evaluated through the larvae path angles.

Cadmium

Biochemical results

Ciprofloxacin

- AChE activity was decreased at 24.5 µg/L suggesting neurotoxicity caused by Cd.
- Cd exposure increased LPO up to 8.16 µg/L, then decreased at the highest concentration (24.5 µg/L), indicating a non-linear oxidative stress response.
- The antioxidant system did not appear to be activated, as no effects were detected in GST, CAT, GPx, or GR activities. However, SOD activity was decreased at the lowest cadmium concentration (0.24 µg/L).

- AChE activity was increased at 33 mg/L suggesting neurotoxicity caused by ciprofloxacin.
- The antioxidant system was activated with significant changes in GST and CAT activities.
- No lipid peroxidation was detected.

Behavioural results

Changes in the proportions of zigzag movements & straight movements suggest effects in the fish swimming patterns.

Exposure to 0.24 and 24.5 µg/L of Cd provoked changes in the proportion of rapid/slow movements.

Exposure to ciprofloxacin decreased the frequency of straight movements.

The proportion of rapid/slow movements were affected in all tested concentrations when comparing to control.

Transcriptomics & Epigenetics results

mRNA abundance

Cadmium

Ciprofloxacin

Biological Processes

KEGG Pathways

The 25 genes commonly affected by Cd and Ciprofloxacin are involved in key metabolic processes, including amino acid, lipid, and xenobiotic metabolism, as well as oxidative stress responses and DNA methylation. Results suggest that both contaminants trigger overlapping disruptions in metabolic and stress-regulatory pathways.

Global DNA methylation results

No effects were observed in Global DNA methylation for both cadmium nor ciprofloxacin.

TAKE-HOME MESSAGE

This study highlights that cadmium and ciprofloxacin, though chemically distinct, induce overlapping molecular and phenotypic effects in zebrafish larvae. Both exposures affected neurotoxicity markers, swimming behaviour, and selectively modulated oxidative stress responses. Importantly, 25 genes were commonly regulated across treatments, associated with core metabolic, oxidative stress, and epigenetic pathways, suggesting potential shared molecular signatures of chemical-induced stress in aquatic organisms.

FURTHER STUDIES

To conduct a multi-omic approach consisting of Transcriptomic (RNA-seq) and Epigenetic (EM-seq) analyses to better elucidate the mode of action of cadmium and ciprofloxacin at a genome-wide level. This integrative strategy will help uncover novel biomarkers and mechanistic insights, improving environmental risk assessment frameworks for aquatic toxicants.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We acknowledge the financial support to CESAM by FCT/MCTES (UIDP/50017/2020 + UIDB/50017/2020 + LA/P/0094/2020) through national funds. EPIBOOST-101078991

